

ENHANCED STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS IN TEACHING STOICHIOMETRY: MILLANAR E-SIM VISUAL LEARNING MODEL

Dr. Victoria C. Millanar

Holy Name University, Dampas District, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13117972>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Enhanced-Strategic Intervention Material (Enhanced-SIM) in teaching Stoichiometry using a Solomon Four Square design. This quasi-experimental research involved 160 Grade 9 students from a private university in Bohol, Philippines. Pre- and post-tests assessed students' performance, while a survey gathered their feedback. Statistical analyses were employed to analyze data and predict outcomes, including paired t-tests, independent means t-tests, and Multiple Linear Regression. Results indicated significant improvements in post-test scores across all three Enhanced-SIM interventions. While mean gains varied among materials, the SIM-Pure text showed significant differences in the Mole Concept, Mole Ratio, and Mass-Mole calculations but not in Mole-Mass and Mass-Mass calculations. Additionally, all three Enhanced-SIMs demonstrated equal impact on gains, suggesting their effectiveness as teaching materials, particularly for factual and single-step problems. However, the study found that the enhancers—visual process (diagram), visual communication (comics), and audiovisual (video)—were insufficient for guiding learners through more complex problems. This led to the development of the Millanar Enhanced-SIM learning model, which highlights the equal impacts of visual process, visual communication, and audiovisual elements on learning outcomes. The study recommends complementing the use of enhanced SIM materials with classroom exploration and critical discussions to foster the integration of various concepts within a cohesive learning framework. This holistic approach ensures a deeper understanding of Stoichiometry and its applications among students.

Keywords: *Solomon Four Square design, Enhanced Intervention Material, Learning Model, Stoichiometry, visual learning model*

INTRODUCTION

Effective science teaching is to make the learning and teaching process meaningful, enjoyable, relevant, and lasting. This goal can be achieved when the pedagogical strategies used in the classrooms are matched with appropriate learning materials. Lessons particularly in science that are hard to imagine, need suitable techniques which can convert abstract ideas into something that the mind can easily manipulate and absorb (Omeje & Ugbo, 2014). Thus, every teacher in this subject area must provide and devise appropriate instructional materials for his/her students to ensure learning.

It is a reality that science teaching has been a challenge for Philippine educators. The performance of students in science has not improved in recent years, as the Department of Education observed a decline in students' science and technology performance in the National Elementary Achievement Test and National Achievement Test results (Bunagan, 2012). Studies show that the insufficiency of instructional materials and the scarcity of science laboratories are among the main factors that account for the low performance of Filipino students. For instance, the lack of quality and engaging textbooks and the lack of science equipment hinder the conduct of scientific investigations and hands-on activities among Filipino pupils. To fill this gap, teachers use their ingenuity to improvise teaching materials. These instructional materials must be appropriate in terms of their factual content, have quality standards in presentation, and apply to the subject matter and the intellectual levels of the students for whom the material is intended. In 2012, Strategic Intervention Material, or SIM was introduced by the Department of Education to supplement the limited books and science teaching tools available.

The researcher deems that the Strategic Intervention Material which DepEd recommends as being successful in improving the academic performance of students in various subjects, could be adapted to teach complicated concepts in science. It may also be used to resolve the gaps in the lack of instructional materials and the declining performance in science. It is only when students maximize their learning in a science classroom that the vision of Philippine science education will be achieved, for this reason, the present study is conducted. By this attempt to make innovative teaching material, the teaching-learning process will be made easier on the part of the teacher and the students. The latter may also find the material more engaging as they learn the concept with fun.

The present study develops and assesses the functionality of an enhanced–Strategic Intervention Material called enhanced SIM in teaching stoichiometry. This learning device patterned after the DepEd SIM is multifaceted, customized, practical, and simplified but it is further added with mental scaffoldings in the form of diagrams, comics, or videos. These visual aids are with proven potential to remove learning obstacles in understanding a topic. According to Lee, et al. (2017), diagrams as visual aids facilitate the development of accurate mental models and significantly improve the instructional efficiency of the subjects. Tatalovic (2009) also found out that comic strips, varying in length, style, and preparation, are considered excellent mediums for interestingly

conveying concepts, and a variety of them are available for science teaching. Moreover, Zarra (2017) concluded that teaching using video is promising because the human brain can process video many times faster than text alone, especially for millennials, whose brains can process even faster. With these enhancers, learning can be more effective and enjoyable, and with reduced cognitive load, the students are facilitated to absorb the concepts despite the complexities of the mental processes.

Stoichiometry is one of the most complicated topics in science which challenges both teachers and students. Every year, teachers look forward to frustrations in teaching the topic because the students find it complex (Kutcy & Schulz, 2006). Similarly, Espinosa et al. (2016) found that misconceptions were discovered in the prominent methods used in pre-service training for teachers. Having taught science for several years, the researcher can attest that stoichiometry is unintelligible, and thus, students regard it as hard. It is least appreciated by most college students, especially those whose background in formula writing and in balancing equations is weak.

In effect, students have a misconception that chemistry is difficult, uninteresting, and irrelevant. Despite students' perspectives on stoichiometry, learning the basics of this subject is a must. One's knowledge of stoichiometry will enable him to pass high-stakes examinations. Stoichiometry may also inspire students to become scientists as it opens up various applications. It is the key to innovations and the discovery of new products (Kutcy & Schulz, 2006).

The researcher believes that the enhanced- SIM in teaching Stoichiometry can make science learning not only fun and easy but more importantly, relevant and lasting. This innovation will hopefully help students to appreciate science and technology and will inspire them to pursue science-related careers to manage the demands of food and other materials in the future.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the functionality of the Enhanced Strategic Intervention Material in teaching Stoichiometry.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry using Strategic Intervention Materials enhanced with:
 - 1.1 pure text;
 - 1.2 comics;
 - 1.3 diagrams; and
 - 1.4 videos?
2. Is there a significant improvement in the students' entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry using the Enhanced Strategic Intervention Materials?
3. Is there a significant mean gain difference in the students' entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry along the four enhanced-SIM?
4. What are the students' feedback on the enhanced-SIM as to its application in science learning?

5. Based on the findings, what theory/model maybe proposed in the study?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. It also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the process of collecting the data, and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical considerations were also discussed.

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically the Solomon Four-Square design, to assess the effectiveness of enhanced strategic intervention materials (SIM) in improving students' understanding of stoichiometry. The set-up included four groups: two for SIM Pure text and two for each experimental group using enhanced SIM materials. While only half of the control and experimental groups underwent pretesting, all groups completed post-tests after the study implementation. Statistical analyses, including t-tests for paired samples and independent samples, were conducted to analyze post-test outcomes and mean gains of the instructional materials. Multiple Linear Regression was used to identify the enhanced SIM material with the most significant impact on learning outcomes, addressing the study's null hypotheses and ensuring a rigorous analysis of the data.

Research Environment and Research Participants

The study was conducted at Holy Name University within the High School Department, specifically involving Grade 9 classrooms. The research took place over two weeks, from February 3-17, 2019. Four Grade 9 classes, labeled A, B, C, and D, were selected for the study, with each class exposed to different instructional materials. Section A served as the control group, using SIM Pure Text. Sections B, C, and D were the experimental groups, exposed to enhanced SIMs, including SIM Comics, SIM Diagram, and SIM Video. The participants were Grade 9 students identified with the help of the Science Coordinator. The study involved pre-testing and post-testing to evaluate the effectiveness of the SIMs. Additionally, feedback was collected from randomly selected students through surveys distributed a week after the study.

Research Instrument

The research instruments used in this study included pre-tests and post-tests, which were encoded and converted into percentages for analysis. A t-test for paired samples was utilized to compare pre-test and post-test scores to determine if there were significant differences. The effectiveness of the enhanced strategic intervention materials (SIMs) was further evaluated using a t-test for independent samples to assess mean gain. Multiple regression statistics were employed to analyze relationships between variables.

Feedback from students was collected through open-ended questions, encoded, and thematically analyzed.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, permission was obtained from the Vice-President for Academic Affairs of Holy Name University. The Principal of the High School Department received a copy of the approved letter to coordinate class schedules with Grade 9 classes. With the assistance of the Science Coordinator, potential participants were identified and grouped according to the study's design. The implementation of the enhanced SIMs took place from February 3-17, 2019, across four classes of identified respondents. The pre-test was administered during the first meeting, followed by the introduction of four enhanced SIMs: SIM Diagram, SIM Comics, SIM Video, and SIM Pure Text.

Grade 9 class sections were labeled A, B, C, and D. Section A served as the control group and was taught with SIM Pure Text, while Sections B, C, and D were taught with enhanced SIM Comics, Diagram, and Video, respectively. To mitigate pre-test score bias, post-test results of pre-tested and non-pre-tested groups for each treatment were compared with the control group. During the study, five topics were covered, with each topic introduced using its corresponding enhanced SIM over one-hour class periods. The researcher facilitated class discussions, distributed study materials, and provided self-evaluation opportunities for students. Enhanced SIMs were exclusively used during class hours to control respondent exposure. A pre-test was conducted for half of the selected classes prior to implementing the enhanced SIMs, as detailed in Table 1 of the schedule.

Table 1: Activities/Topic Schedule

Schedule	ACTIVITIES/TOPICS
Day 1	Pre-test
Day 2-3	The Mole Concept
Day 4-5	The Mole Ratio
Day 6-7	Mole-Mass Calculations
Day 8-9	Mass-Mole Calculations
Day 10-11	Mass-Mass Calculations
Day 12	Post-test

After the observation period, a post-test measured students' exit performance, followed by the distribution of survey questionnaires to randomly selected students a week later to gather feedback. Throughout the study, strict adherence to ethical considerations ensured data integrity and confidentiality. Participants were assured that their performance wouldn't affect their science grades, and those chosen for the feedback survey were informed that there were no right or wrong answers regarding their opinions. Pre- and post-test results were statistically analyzed, while feedback questionnaire

responses were collected, encoded, and categorized by themes to identify opportunities and challenges experienced during treatment exposure using correct qualitative procedures.

Data Analysis

In this study, the raw data from the pre and post tests were encoded according to topics converted into percentages and tabulated. The data in tables were analysed using T-test for paired samples since each subject was measured twice, during the pre-test and in the post test. The test statistic for paired samples is used to find out if a difference exists between the means of the pre-test and post-test. In the interpretation, the level of significance was at 95% or a p value =.05 and if there is a difference in favour of the post-test, then the treatment or intervention is effective. However, if there is no significant difference then the treatment or intervention is not effective.

The formula used was:

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{n}}{n(n-1)}}$$

Where: D = the mean difference between the pre-test and the post-test
 $\sum D^2$ = the sum of the squares of the difference between the pre-test and the post test
 $\sum D$ = the summation of the difference between the pre-test and the post test
 n = the sample size

To determine the mean gain of the enhanced –SIMs, the pre-test results were subtracted from the post-test outcomes to get the difference and t-test of independent samples is employed. The relationship of the variables was tested with Multiple Regression Statistics.

On students' feedback, open-ended questions were given, and responses were encoded and arranged by themes, analysed and summarised in vignettes.

RESULTS

5.1 Students' Entry and Exit Performance in Stoichiometry using the Enhanced-SIM

The entry and exit performances of Grade 9 respondents were determined from their scores in the pre and post-tests. These scores were converted into percentages and scaled accordingly to give the appropriate description of their knowledge on Mole Concept, Mole Ratio, Mole – Mass – Mole calculations.

Table 2: Students Entry and Exit Performance using the SIM – Pure Text

(Percentage Score, n=20)

Topics	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
Mole Concept	35.85	Low	50.10	Satisfactory
Mole Ratio	27.60	Low	38.35	Low
Mole – Mass	14.25	Very low	22.55	Low
Mass – Mole	22.50	Very low	30.75	Low
Mass – Mass	15.05	Very low	22.50	Low
Average	23.05	Low	32.84	Low

Scale: 0-20 very low, 21-40 low, 41-60 satisfactory, 61-80 high, 81+ very high

In using plain SIM Pure Text, the pre-test scores ranged from 35.85% for Mole Concept to 14.25% for Mole-Mass, indicating low to very low entry knowledge in stoichiometry. Post-test scores increased, with the highest at 51.10% for Mole Concept and the lowest at 22.50% for Mole-Mass calculations. However, the average pre-test score of 23.05% only increased to 32.84%, still categorized as low performance. This suggests that plain SIM with pure texts did not significantly improve respondents' performance, particularly in comprehension and problem-solving areas like Mole-Mass, Mass-Mole, and Mass-Mass calculations.

This aligns with Chandrasegaran et al. (2009) findings on teachers' frustration due to students' difficulty retaining information in stoichiometry. Unlike other studies in Mathematics, General Science, and Chemistry, the use of plain SIM Pure Text did not enhance participants' performance, reflecting a lack of motivation and difficulty in connecting information.

This implies that instructional materials in SIM format with pure texts alone may not effectively improve students' understanding of stoichiometry topics. Enhancements are needed to contextualize concepts and provide scaffolding for students to anchor their understanding.

Table 3: Students Entry and Exit Performance using the Enhanced SIM Comics
(Percentage Score, n=20)

Topics	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
Mole Concept	25.85	Low	68.35	High
Mole Ratio	14.25	Very low	41.65	Satisfactory
Mole - Mass	10.95	Very low	48.25	Satisfactory
Mass - Mole	10.00	Very low	25.85	Low
Mass - Mass	11.05	Very low	29.10	Low
Average	14.25	Very Low	42.64	Satisfactory

Scale: 0-20 very low, 21-40 low, 41-60 satisfactory, 61-80 high, 81+ very high

Table 3 suggests that enhanced SIM comics effectively convey stoichiometry concepts, particularly Mole Concept, resulting in improved performance. However, when

topics become more complex, like adding mass as a variable, confusion arises, leading to lower scores. This underscores the need to complement enhanced SIM comics with additional teaching techniques for complex lessons.

These findings align with Green and Meyers (2010), who found that comics improve reading comprehension and communicate complex subjects effectively. Similarly, McCloud (1994) noted that comics can convey science concepts realistically. However, comics alone may not suffice for complicated topics requiring intricate procedures.

Table 4: Students Entry and Exit Performance using the enhanced SIM Diagram
(Percentage Score, n=80)

Topics	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
Mole Concept	20.85	Low	71.70	High
Mole Ratio	19.20	Very low	43.40	Satisfactory
Mole-Mass	14.30	Very low	50.00	Satisfactory
Mass-Mole	10.95	Very low	48.25	Low
Mass-Mass	15.85	Very low	40.85	Satisfactory
Average	16.23	Very low	50.85	Satisfactory

Scale: 0-20 very low, 21-40 low, 41-60 satisfactory, 61-80 high, 81+ very high

The use of enhanced SIM diagrams proved effective in improving students' performance in the post-test. Respondents easily deciphered instructions in the diagrams, recalling prerequisite steps for complex situations, as evidenced by satisfactory scores in more intricate topics like Mole-Mass and Mass-Mass calculations. The diagrams provided mental scaffoldings for new lessons and guided students through the process and expected outcomes, resulting in improved performance with reduced mental effort.

These findings align with Lee et al. (2013), who demonstrated that diagrams facilitate the development of accurate mental models, enhancing instructional efficiency. Incorporating diagrams with text in the SIM serves dual roles in students' conceptual learning—textual and visual—which complements each other, as concluded by Dahar and Faize (2011).

Table 5: Students' Entry and Exit Performance using the Enhanced SIM Video
(Percentage Score, n=20)

Topics	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
Mole Concept	26.50	Low	74.10	High
Mole Ratio	20.90	Low	50.05	Satisfactory
Mole-Mass	16.65	Very low	47.45	Satisfactory
Mass-Mole	17.55	Very low	31.65	Low
Mass-Mass	11.75	Very low	26.65	Low
Average	18.67	Very low	45.98	Satisfactory

Scale: 0-20 very low, 21-40 low, 41-60 satisfactory, 61-80 high, 81+ very high

Table 5 displays the entry and exit performance of the group exposed to enhanced SIM videos. Scores increased across all topics, with the highest improvement observed in Mole Concept. The enhanced SIM video aided respondents by clarifying processes and outcomes through expert discussions and visuals, allowing them to organize their thoughts. Learners benefited from audio-visual learning, comprehending complex stoichiometric topics step-by-step. These findings align with Mendoza, et al. (2015), who found video presentations highly effective for student learning and concluded that virtual learning environments support learning. However, they contrast with Kidwai et al. (2001), who suggested that videos may overload cognitive processes when combined with visual scaffoldings and animations.

5. 2 Significant Improvement of the Participants' Entry and Exit Performances in Stoichiometry using the Enhanced- SIM

To guide in the interpretation of the results, t-test of correlated means at $\alpha = 0.05$ was used in the study. Thus, if the p value is lower than $\alpha = 0.05$, the hypothesis is rejected and interpreted as *significant* while if the p value is higher than $\alpha = 0.05$, the hypothesis is accepted and interpreted as *not significant*.

Tables 6-9 show the significant improvement on the performance of Grade 9 student-participants using the plain SIM-pure text, enhanced -SIM diagram, enhanced-SIM comics and enhanced-SIM video respectively. In the analysis of the significant improvement, it was made sure that the post- tests results were not affected by the learners' exposure to the pre-test through a two-way analysis of variance as suggested in the Solomon- Four Group design. All groups yielded *not significant* which means that the post tests have been sensitized.

Table 6: Significant Improvement in the students' Entry and Exit performance using SIM – Pure Text (Percentage Score, n=20, $\alpha = 0.05$)

Topics	Pre-test	Post-test	T-test	P value	Decision
Mole Concept	35.85	50.1	1.851	0.08	Accept, Not Sig
Mole Ratio	27.6	38.35	1.773	0.092	Accept, Not Sig
Mole - Mass	14.25	22.5	1.867	0.077	Accept, Not Sig
Mass - Mole	22.5	30.75	1.38	0.184	Accept, Not Sig
Mass-Mass	15.05	22.5	1.897	0.077	Accept, Not Sig

H₀: There is no significant improvement in the entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry using the enhanced SIM

In the SIM Pure Text group, post-test scores were higher than pre-test scores, indicating numerical improvement in performance. However, statistical analysis revealed that p values for all topics were greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, indicating non-significant improvements. This suggests that the use of plain SIM Pure Text did not significantly enhance respondents' performance in stoichiometry. Figueroa (1998) suggested that students struggle with stoichiometry when it's divorced from real-world applications. Additionally, White et al. (2009) noted that multi-stepped calculations are challenging to grasp mentally. This indicates that pure text alone is insufficient for improving students' understanding of stoichiometry concepts. It fails to guide them through multi-stepped calculations and lacks contextualization. Enhancing lesson presentations to include real-world examples may better direct students and improve comprehension.

Table 7: Significant Improvement in the students' Entry and Exit performance using the enhanced-SIM Comics (Percentage Score , n=20, $\alpha =0.05$)

Topics	Pre test	Post test	T -Test	P value	Decision
Mole Concept	25.85	68.35	10.053	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole Ratio	14.25	41.65	5.286	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole -Mass	10.95	48.25	7.275	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mass -Mole	10.0	25.85	4.838	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mass-Mass	11.05	29.10	3.865	0.0001	Reject, Sig

H₀: There is no significant improvement in the entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry using the enhanced SIM

In the enhanced-SIM comics group, post-test scores exceeded pre-test scores, and statistical analysis showed p values below $\alpha = 0.05$ for all topics, rejecting the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant improvement in students' understanding of stoichiometry, particularly in Mole Concept, Mole Ratio, Mole-Mass, Mass-Mole, and Mass-Mass calculations. This aligns with Steiner's (1986) assertion that appropriate teaching methods facilitate comprehension, allowing students to organize their work effectively (Kutcy & Schulz, 2006). Similarly, Espinosa (2014) found that enhanced SIM, when integrated strategically into classroom practice, enhances learners' grasp of scientific concepts. The enhanced SIM comics engage students through contextualized

comic strips, offering clear instructions for problem-solving while adhering to the SIM format, simplifying procedures and solidifying concepts.

Table 8: Significant Improvement in the students' Entry and Exit using enhanced-SIM Diagram (Percentage Score, n =20, $\alpha = 0.05$)

Topics	Pre test	Post test	T-test	P value	Decision
Mole Concept	20.85	71.75	9.583	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole Ratio	19.2	43.4	5.647	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole-Mass	14.3	50.0	6.517	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mass-Mole	10.95	48.25	7.275	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mass-Mass	15.85	40.85	5.278	0.0000	Reject, Sig

H₀: There is no significant improvement in the entry and exit performance in Stoichiometry using the enhanced SIM

The enhanced-SIM diagram group exhibited higher post-test scores compared to pre-test scores, with all topics showing p values below $\alpha = 0.05$ through paired-samples t-tests, indicating significant improvement in stoichiometry performance. This aligns with Lee et al.'s (2013) findings, suggesting that diagrams aid in developing accurate mental models, enhancing instructional efficiency. The incorporation of texts in the SIM serves dual roles, textual and visual, supporting students' conceptual learning. Similarly, Liu (2012) suggests that diagrams complement textual explanations, aiding comprehension of complex concepts. The study confirms the effectiveness of diagrams in the SIM for enhancing stoichiometry understanding, providing mental scaffolding and facilitating easier comprehension compared to textual instructions alone.

Table 9: The Significant Improvement on the Performance of Grade 9 Respondents Using the Enhanced SIM Video (Percentage Score, n =20, $\alpha = 0.05$)

Topics	Pretest	Post test	T-test	P value	Decision
Mole Concept	26.5	74.1	12.45	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole Ratio	20.9	50.05	5.045	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mass-Mole	16.65	47.45	5.168	0.0000	Reject, Sig
Mole-Mass	17.55	31.65	2.542	0.0200	Reject, Sig
Mass-Mass	11.75	26.65	3.448	0.0030	Reject, Sig

The exposure to enhanced-SIM videos led to increased post-test scores, with p values below 0.05 in all topics, rejecting the null hypothesis and indicating significant improvement in respondents' performance. The video component of the enhanced-SIM material allowed students to clarify processes and outcomes through expert discussions and visuals, facilitating organization of thoughts. This aided comprehension of complex stoichiometric topics. These findings align with Singh 's (2004) conclusion that audio-visual clips enhance problem-solving skills and with Mendoza, et al. (2015) assertion

regarding the effectiveness of video presentations in learning. Jain (2015) also supports this, highlighting the supportive nature of virtual learning environments. However, this contrasts with Kidwai et al.'s (2004) claim that videos are only beneficial for factual knowledge and not for higher order thinking skills, suggesting a potential cognitive overload with combined visual scaffoldings and animations.

4. 3 Mean Gain Difference in the students' Entry and Exit in Stoichiometry among the Enhanced -SIMs

Table 10: The Mean Gain Difference in the students' Entry and Exit performance in Stoichiometry among the Four Enhanced-SIMs

	Mean Gain	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value	Decision
Mole Concept					
Pure Text (Control)	9.3750	25.60935			
Enhanced-SIM Comics	31.8750	14.32414	3.429	0.001	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Diagram	38.8158	18.58480	3.970	0.000	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Video	36.8421	12.12900	3.833	0.000	Reject Ho
Mole Ratio					
Pure Text (Control)	8.1250	20.38890			
Enhanced-SIM Comics	20.6250	17.33712	2.089	0.043	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Diagram	20.3750	17.88719	1.999	0.050	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Video	21.2500	18.18219	2.149	0.038	Reject Ho
Mole Mass					
Pure Text (Control)	6.2500	17.44352			
Enhanced-SIM Comics	28.1250	17.14633	4.000	0.000	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Diagram	23.0263	20.09662	2.788	0.008	Reject Ho
Enhanced-SIM Video	22.3684	19.79888	2.701	0.010	Reject Ho
Mass-Mole					
Pure Text (Control)	6.2500	20.07388			
Enhanced-SIM Comics	11.2500	11.39887	0.969	0.339	Accept Ho
Enhanced-SIM Diagram	7.5000	18.31738	0.206	0.838	Accept Ho
Enhanced-SIM Video	8.1250	17.80514	0.313	0.756	Accept Ho
Mass Mass					
Pure Text (Control)	15.0000	18.84843			
Enhanced-SIM Comics	13.7500	15.65458	0.228	0.821	Accept Ho
Enhanced-SIM Diagram	19.3750	15.42970	0.228	0.821	Accept Ho
Enhanced-SIM Video	12.5000	14.04879	0.476	0.637	Accept Ho

Table 10 compares the effectiveness of different enhanced-SIMs with plain text in Stoichiometry topics using a t-test for independent samples.

Enhanced-SIM Comics yielded the highest mean gains in Mole-ratio, Mole-mass, Mass-Mole, and Mass-mass topics, indicating improved learning outcomes through visualized instructions. This aligns with Kim et al.'s (2012) findings on the effectiveness of comics in enhancing comprehension and performance. Enhanced-SIM Diagrams

showed the highest mean gain in Mole Concept and Mass-Mass, aiding learners in visualizing relationships and boosting confidence in problem-solving, consistent with Jaoude & Barakat (2000) research. Enhanced-SIM Videos demonstrated significant mean gains across all topics, guiding learners through auditory and visual channels and facilitating relevant associations for memory and recall, in line with Raiyn, J. (2016) findings.

However, significant differences in mean gains between enhanced-SIMs and Pure text were only observed in Mole Concept, Mole Ratio, and Mole-Mass topics, indicating limited functionality of enhancers in more complex problems like Mass-Mole and Mass-Mass, where multi-step solutions and higher-order thinking skills are required. This underscores the importance of aligning teaching strategies with the complexity of the topic and integrating group exploration and critical discourse within a joint learning framework, as noted by Gilboy et al. (2015). Overall, enhanced SIMs, especially those with visual enhancements, outperform plain text in teaching Stoichiometry.

DISCUSSION

Findings

Students' Feedback on the Use of Enhanced – SIM

Twenty randomly selected students from the experimental groups were asked to give their feedback on the use of the instructional materials. Two open ended questions were given to gather the experiences while using the enhanced-SIMS. The first question focused on what they like most, while the second question on what they do not like most in the instructional material. The responses were collected, coded and grouped according to emerging themes.

When the respondents were asked “*What did you like most in the use of enhanced-SIM?*”, four groups of answers emerged.

Simplifies the Lesson

In the use of the enhanced-SIM, the students' remarked:

“It enhances our method of learning, it makes it simpler and easier in solving moles (8), it was very detailed and very good learning material (2), by making the lesson easier (4), the lesson become easy (11) and a detailed explanation in regards to stoichiometry with solutions and examples (6).”

These responses signify that the material was able to simplify the complicated steps in solving stoichiometric problems. The detailed explanations provided in the sample problems made the lesson easily understood. The enhancers provided the learners a guide on the steps based on the underlying concepts. They tend to memorize the procedure easily and were able to answer the problems correctly. This finding is consistent with Jaoude & Barakat (2000) when they mentioned that students perform better when asked to memorize set of steps to solve stoichiometric problems and states

that more effort needs to be done to ensure conceptual understanding. Since the approach was detailed and simple, cognitive overload was reduced and enhanced the learning process.

Provides Direction

Secondly, the respondents claimed that the material has provided them directions that helped them to study on their own. The easy-to-follow diagrams and the simplified steps gave them a road-map which brought each learner to a situation where he/she wants to arrive at based on the what is given and what is desired in the stoichiometric problem. They commented that:

“It takes me to path I want to choose (3), it helps me to provide a preview on what we expected to learn (7), I like the most is when the moles were added , it helps me the right path (9), I like the guidelines given on how to use the enhanced-SIM- it helped me understand more(10).”

This means that they were guided how to attain the desired outcome with the given inputs. The preview provided in each lesson, allowed the learners to have a glimpse of the whole process from start to end and what needs to be done along the way like the necessary conversion from one point to another. The diagrams and comics were used to illustrate visually the processes, outcomes and the variations characterizing these processes. In visual learning, lesser cognitive tasks are involved, this is the reason why the students commented that the enhanced-SIM material improved their learning and make the process simpler and easier understood. This observation is consistent with the findings of Maddrell (2015) in conceptual approach in teaching. He stated that when students are introduced to the whole picture of ideas, and taught how to organize and categorize information, they will understand and have opportunities for innovation, creativity and better productivity.

Arouses Students' Interest

The third reason why the students like the enhanced-SIM is the ability of the material to arouse their interest. They said:

“It is keeping the subject more interesting (1), Helps me understand better (12), Gives little background about moles and arouses my interest in stoichiometry (15)”

The presentation of the concept in comics, diagram or video keeps the subject more interesting. The story line in comics gives them a little recall on the concepts of moles, the starting conditions as well as the required conditions at the end, thus, it has provided focus at each point in the problem-solving procedure. According to Tatalovic (2014), comic strips are considered excellent medium for conveying concepts in an interesting way. On the other hand, this result also confirmed the findings of Cuevas et al. (2017), that diagrams are beneficial on learners' cognitive and metacognitive processes where higher level of performance can be achieved with less mental effort. Moreover, videos help the learners make more relevant associations with memory and recall Raiyn (2016).

Provides Assurance

Finally, the functionality of the enhanced SIM modules was on the assurance it provides which allowed the students to answer the problems on their own. The respondents commented:

“I had a guide to double check my tracks when I answer (5). Assured me that I am in the right path (13). It helps me answered the questions and activities without help (14)”

The material allowed the learners to double check the solutions as they keep track on the step-by-step instructions. Visual scaffoldings which complement the instructions impact students' learning performance. This is important because with increased confidence, students' ability to solve complex problems is improved. Each step is given a detailed instruction and a simple to follow recipe needed in transforming formula mass to moles or vice-versa. As Jaoude & Barakat (2000) suggested, the algorithm method nurtures students' confidence and helps them solve problems efficiently. By learning the secret recipes or short cuts in solving stoichiometric problems, students can answer during examinations and decipher problems in real-life situations with ease and confidence.

Based on the gathered responses, the respondents said that the use of enhanced SIMs had simplified the lesson, provided direction, aroused their interest and gave them assurance. The material was detailed in terms of presentation and was provided with relevant sample problems that were easy to follow.

On the second question, *“What did you not like most in the use of the enhanced SIMs?”* the respondents gave answers which were directed to only one emerging theme, which is time.

They commented that:

“It's time consuming and makes the person uninterested if it takes too much time (2), not fully implemented because of lack of time (8), time consuming (5,9,10,14), the discussion became boring memorizing the steps(13), some of the concepts were not explained thoroughly no more time(#8), there are steps that are confusing but some only(5), illustrating the relationship between the variables lacks time to understand further(18).”

It was observed that the one-hour exposure of the instructional material to the students resulted to other topics not being understood well, they get bored on some steps because they lack time to understand the relationships of the variables. Time constraints prevented them to fully understand the concepts. True to Maddrell's (2015) claim, concept learning is time consuming because it will take much longer for information to be acquired.

These results imply that the functionality of enhanced-SIMs can still be maximized when their use is not limited by time. Although they can be used in the classroom for actual teaching, they are also recommended for individualized learning or as a supplementary learning material which can be studied outside the structured school hours.

Millanar e-SIM Visual Learning Model

Based on the results of the study, the Millanar e-SIM Visual learning model is formulated. This model shows the relationships of enhanced-SIM Comics, enhanced-SIM Diagram and enhanced-SIM Video to the over-all learning outcomes in Stoichiometry.

Multiple Linear Regression was used to determine the relationship between the three enhanced-SIMs as the independent variables against the learning outcome as the dependent variable. By comparing the coefficients of the three enhanced-SIMs against the intercept, which was the mean of the reference, the predictor or most effective enhanced-material was identified.

Table 11: Multiple Linear Regression Results showing the relationships of the enhanced-SIMS *Dependent variable: gain Independent Variables: e-SIM comics, e-SIM diagram, e-SIM Video* $Gain = 12.5 + 15.85 \text{ comics} + 14.65 \text{ diagram} + 14.75 \text{ video}$

Parameters	Estimates	Std Error	DF	T-Stats	Pvalue
Intercept	12.15	2.525	76	4.8117	<0.0001
e-SIM Comics	15.85	3.571	76	4.4385	<0.0001
e-SIM Diagram	14.65	3.571	76	4.1025	0.0001
e-SIM Video	14.75	3.571	76	4.1305	<0.0001

The results indicate that enhanced-SIM Comics, enhanced-SIM Diagrams, and enhanced-SIM Videos all have coefficients higher than the intercept, suggesting equal effectiveness in improving learning outcomes. These materials utilize visual and audio-visual channels to enhance student understanding.

Visual learning through diagrams, comics, and videos allows students to visualize concepts and processes, aiding in comprehension and memory recall. However, their effectiveness is limited to factual and single-step problems, and they may not sufficiently support higher-order thinking tasks. The enhanced Strategic Intervention Material's significant improvement in learning outcomes can be attributed to visual learning, which allows students to process information effectively through images, diagrams, and videos. However, these materials may not fully support tasks requiring higher cognitive skills.

Millanar Enhanced-SIM Learning Model

Learning is a mental process that demonstrates meaningful outcomes necessary in making decisions, evaluation, logical thinking and problem solving. As observed in the study, the following table summarizes the functional characteristics of Diagrams, Comics, and Video when they are used in an instructional material as visual learning enhancers. These characteristics are in terms of their definition, mental processes, capability, advantages, affective reward and their impacts to the learning outcomes.

Table 12: Characteristics of Visual Learning through enhanced-SIMs ENHANCERS in the SIMs

	Diagrams	Comics	Video
DEFINITION	Organise information in meaningful patterns	Contextualise concepts through dialogues related to students' experience	Artistically use animations and sounds
MENTAL PROCESS	Visual-Process	Visual-Communication	Visual- Audio
CAPABILITY	Reading is quicker to read and ideas are easier to memorise	Reading comprehension is improved	Multi-channel learning through the auditory and visual
ADVANTAGES	Conceptual understanding with less comprehension skills required	Stimulate interests and increase engagement in a comprehensible material	More insights are learned when repeated again and again
AFFECTIVE REWARD	Assurance and guide towards right direction	Effective communication between the material and the learner	More relevant association with experiences
OUTCOMES	Mental model higher level of performance with less mental effort	Greater students' interest and better understanding of lessons	Acquire a range of transferable skills and boosts students' achievement level

In conclusion, diagrams, comics, and videos serve as valuable visual tools that enhance learning outcomes by engaging students and facilitating comprehension. These pedagogical strategies, incorporated into enhanced-SIMs, make learning enjoyable and effective.

Enhanced-SIM Diagrams organize information visually, aiding in quicker comprehension and promoting conceptual understanding with less mental effort. Comics in enhanced-SIM Comics contextualize concepts through engaging dialogues, improving reading comprehension and fostering student interest. Enhanced-SIM Videos utilize visual-audio learning to capture student interest and promote insightful behaviour.

Recommendations

Based on these insights, the Millanar e-SIM Visual Learning Model is proposed to guide Stoichiometry teaching:

- 1. Prep and Leap:** Strong foundational knowledge is crucial for advancing in Stoichiometry. Learners must master basic concepts and mathematical operations before tackling more complex topics.
- 2. Furnish to Finish:** Each topic in Stoichiometry builds on the previous one, requiring mastery of prerequisite skills for progression. Teachers must ensure learners are fully equipped with necessary concepts and skills.
- 3. Sustain and Gain:** Performance may temporarily decrease during transition to more challenging topics but will improve with time. Appropriate instructional materials sustain student interest and engagement, facilitating learning.

The journey to mastering Stoichiometry requires a strong foundation, continuous skill development, and engaging instructional materials like enhanced-SIM Diagrams, Comics, and Videos.

Conclusions

The three enhanced Strategic Intervention Materials were functional as an instructional scaffolding which supported in learning the concepts. When applied correctly, they can improve students' performance in stoichiometry. The diagrams in the enhanced-SIM diagram help visualise the textual instructions and serve as an accurate mental guide to understand the concept so that higher level of performance was achieved with less mental effort. The comic strips in enhanced-SIM comics have aroused the respondents' interests and effectively conveyed the target concept so that a simplified approach is understood in solving stoichiometric problems. Similarly, the video clip used in enhanced-SIM video has clarified the concepts as they regarded it as an expert's opinion with authority. Aside from arousing their interest, the enhanced –SIM video was also self-directing. The trio of enhanced Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) functioned as pedagogical scaffolds, bolstering the comprehension of stoichiometry concepts. Appropriately implemented, these materials hold promise for augmenting student performance in this domain. The inclusion of diagrams within the enhanced-SIM Diagram facilitated the visualization of textual directives, furnishing learners with precise mental guides for concept assimilation. This visual augmentation mitigated cognitive load, leading to heightened performance attainment with diminished cognitive effort. Similarly, the integration of comic strips within enhanced-SIM Comics captivated the attention of participants, effectively communicating targeted principles. This visually engaging format streamlined intricate problem-solving methodologies, rendering the content more accessible and digestible. The incorporation of video clips in enhanced-SIM Video elucidated complex concepts, offering learners authoritative insights akin to expert guidance. Beyond mere engagement, the enhanced-SIM video afforded students a degree of self-directed learning, fostering autonomy and active participation in the educational process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

REFERENCES

- Bunagan, F. (2012). Science Intervention Material. Retrieved from <http://www.slideshare.net/felix-bunagan/strategic-intervention-material>
- Chandrasegaran, A. L., Treagust, D. F., Waldrip, B. G., & Chandrasegaran, A. (2009). Students' dilemmas in reaction stoichiometry problem solving: deducing the limiting reagent in chemical reactions. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 10(1), 14-23.
- Dahar, M. A., & Faize, F. A. (2011). Effect of the availability and the use of instructional material on academic performance of students in Punjab (Pakistan). *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*, 11, 15-26.
- Espinosa, A. A. (2014). Strategic intervention material-based instruction, learning approach and students' performance in chemistry. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 2(1).
- Espinosa, A. A., España, R. C. N., & Marasigan, A. C. (2016). Investigating pre-service chemistry teachers' problem solving strategies: Towards developing a framework in teaching stoichiometry. *Journal of Education in Science Environment and Health*, 2(2), 104-124.
- Gilboy, M. B., Heinerichs, S., & Pazzaglia, G. (2015). Enhancing student engagement using the flipped classroom. *Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior*, 47(1), 109-114.
- Green, M. J., & Myers, K. R. (2010). Graphic medicine: Use of Comics in Medical Education and Patient Care. *British Medical Journal*, 340, 863. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.c863>
- Jain, P. (2015). Virtual learning environment. *International Journal in IT & Engineering*, 3(5), 75-84.
- Jaoude, S. B., & Barakat, H. (2000). Secondary school students' difficulties with stoichiometry. *School Science Review*, 81(296), 1.
- Kidwai, K., Munyofu, M., Swain, W. J., Ausman, B. D., Lin, H., & Dwyer, F. (2001). Effect of Visual Scaffolding and Animation on Students' Performance on Measures of Higher Order Learning. Association for Educational Communications and Technology.
- Kim, Dae Hyun, Jang, Hae Gwon, Dong, Sun Shin, Sun-Ja Kim, Chang Young Yoo & Min Suk Chung (2012). Science Comic Strips. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 1(2), 65-75. ISSN 1927-5250 E-ISSN 1927-5269. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/jel.v1n2p65>
- Kutcy, C. E. B., & Schulz, R. (2006). Why are beginning teachers frustrated with the teaching profession?. *McGill Journal of Education/Revue des sciences de l'éducation de McGill*, 41(1).
- Lee, J., Lim, C., & Kim, H. (2017). Development of an instructional design model for flipped learning in higher education. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 65, 427-453.

- Maddrell, J. A. (2015). Designing authentic educational experiences through virtual service learning. *The Design of Learning Experience: Creating the Future of Educational Technology*, 215-229.
- Mendoza, G. L. L., Caranto, L. C., & David, J. J. T. (2015). Effectiveness of video presentation to students' learning. *International Journal of Nursing Science*, 5(2), 81-86.
- McCloud, S. (1994). *Understanding comics: The invisible Art*. New York, NY: William Morrow Paperbacks. Accepted 30 Nov 2010, Published online: 12 May 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2010.545873>
- Raiyn, J. (2016). The Role of Visual Learning in Improving Students' High-Order Thinking Skills. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(24), 115-121.
- Steiner, R. P. (1986). Teaching stoichiometry. In *Journal of Chemical Education* (Vol. 63, Issue 12, p. 1048). American Chemical Society (ACS). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed063p1048.1>
- Singh, C. (2004, September). Interactive video tutorials for enhancing problem-solving, reasoning, and meta-cognitive skills of introductory physics students. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 720, No. 1, pp. 177-180). American Institute of Physics.
- Tatalovic, M. (2009). Science comics as tools for science education and communication: A brief, exploratory study. *Journal of Science Communication*, 8(4), 1-17.
- White, J., Dougherty, B., Schmidt, D. C., & Benavides Cuevas, D. F. (2009). Automated reasoning for multi-step feature model configuration problems. In *SPLC 2009: 13th International Software Product Line Conference (2009)*, p 11-20. ACM.
- Zarra, E. J. (2017). *The entitled generation: Helping teachers teach and reach the minds and hearts of Generation Z*. Rowman & Littlefield.